

Enhancing user authentication for mobile wallet using cryptographic algorithm

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Abstract

Mobile payment is widely used payment methodology adopted by the users in the recent days, Contactless payment is one among the technology used recently with the NFC enabled devices. Contactless payment is nothing but a secure method for customers to purchase products via smartcards by using RFID or NFC enabled device. In contactless payment system have many benefits to both customers and merchant as well as it has the disadvantage security risk in authentication and transaction. Henceforth, a cryptographic measures to achieve security in mobile wallet is proposed.

Keywords: *Cryptography, NFC enabled device, POS, protocol.*

1. Introduction

Mobile wallet can store all the information can be stored virtually in mobile devices and moreover its convenient for the mobile users for mobile payment with merchant service provider. In mobile payment, a mobile device is used to initiate, authorize and confirm an exchange of currency for goods and services. Mobile payment needs a terminal to transaction and authentication to check whether it is legitimate user or not. Mobile payments are using point of sale(POS) in NFC enabled device and account based for the transaction between the customer and merchant which involves direct purchase of goods and services. There are two types of payment are categorized in mobile payment that is proximity payment and remote payment. In proximity payment refers contactless payment which is using a terminal like(NFC)Near-field communication and it thus becoming a new payment factor. For example, to make an online purchase by swiping the mobile device over a contactless NFC reader. Remote payment is nothing which can use mobile as device for transaction and is used to authenticate personal information stored immediately. Proximity payment by NFC enabled device which is not increase to high. The advanced infrastructure is lack in proximity mobile payments. In this NFC enabled devices which can have three types and its works depend on the user needs. This mobile payment system has many pros as well as cons such as payment system are security, privacy, loyalty, cost, cheaper credit and better trekking inventory. The disadvantage of this payment system are Hardware incompatibility, Device failure, cost, Phone is prone to be theft and Difficult to read terms and conditions. Even though it provides good security user authentication is considered as most important one. If the system seems to be insecure to authenticate the users, it leads to destruction till end and need to lose all.

2. Related works and background

Related works

The focus of this work is that NFC enabled device and POS terminal which should be free from attacks. Here the cryptographic mechanism and protocol which is used to resist attacks on the network as well as user authentication and transaction .In this NFC enabled device the proposed method which can be used to resist this kind of attacks. The first system, called mFerio[11], was proposed. This system which can be based on P2P mobile system which can make the mobile transaction but which will be connected with the back end server and it depends on digital cash. The authors about payment system is very secure and usability than traditional system. The mobile payment system which provides two based on NFC mobile based system. In terms of security, the proposed system relies on two aspects, like security on mobile device and the security for on the user of the mobile device. For security on mobile devices ,used password mechanism like PIN, code and pattern etc., The details of storage and the authentication of users will be stored on SE(secure element)The authentication plays an important role to authenticate the user to the mobile phone for mobile payment. Second, the user should be aware of malicious users and malicious attack before communicating and transact with it. Here the system is using two touch protocol and this has two phases, the first phase which can prove its identity to each other and the second phase which is for transaction. The proposed system analyzed like its having the secure transaction, authentication by two touch protocol but its difficult to prevent and predict the attacks .The number of steps are needed to complete the transaction and its computational rate is high.

The second proposed protocol [2] by Kadambi, Li, and Karp a protocol is based on NFC enabled device which can use secure element for transaction and it provides the authorization token to the user using EMV standards. Here public key infrastructure (PKI) is being deployed in the protocol is used where the pair of keys should be stored in the secure element. This PKI which secures the transaction between end to end transaction. Moreover, PKI which is more secure for mobile phone security issues.

The third proposed protocol uses Global system by W. Chen et al[3] for communication authentication for transaction In this protocol both the user's phone and the POS terminal have to be registered to the same Mobile Operator (MO).Here triple authentication

method can be used and the pre-shared key which is stored in the secure element as well as phone. Here using A3 and key used to authenticate the phone.

An improved version of previously mentioned protocol which can provides new steps included and executed before transaction in secure element and it is used to generate new keys. The generated keys which can be used for the next set of protocol .This improved version of protocol will add the random values which can be used to increase the strength of security against attacks. Both protocols which can provide security for transaction as well as it prevents attacks but it's not much secure. Storing the pre-shared will be providing positivity for the security of storage. According to W. Chen et al. and Saed the protocol will be wanted level of trust from the customer and MO will take care of security in case of information privacy. The disadvantage of this protocol which is more complexity than other payment system.

A secure and privacy preserving mobile wallet with outsourced verification in cloud server & the improvement was published on 2016. PSP, customer ,merchant and untrusted server which are the main entities in the system. unforgeability, anonymity, traceability and non-repudiation. should be satisfied. Traceability which helps to know about the real identity of the customer or merchant. Because of the untrusted server for communication, it's not secure for merchant.

Background

The NFC enabled phone which can have three modes
 Every mode in this NFC enabled device which will have different purpose

1. Read/write mode
2. Peer to peer mode
3. Card emulation mode

Reader/writer mode

This mode which can act as reader to read tags of cards. It uses collision avoidance mechanism and it detects a tags which is close to the terminal or proximity. The NFC enabled device which can read the data using read/write mode operations. This mode which can be internally divided into two types ie.reader mode and writer mode. In reader mode, which can read the data from an NFC tags and it has the program which performs the requested data to the initiator. In writer mode, the mobile acts as the initiator which can write the data to the tag. If the data is already in the tag, newly data which can be written. The algorithm is found for the updation of the existing tag for the initiator .

Application

1. Smart poster
2. Remote marketing
3. Remote shopping
4. Social networking and location based services

Peer to peer

Peer to Peer mode which can be for exchange information like text message and kind of data. This mode which can be standardized information to define the initiator and target device for the communication and it is identical to LLCP. Application which runs on application layer take a decision. In Peer to peer mode called bidirectional duplex channel which can have two modes that is active and passive .Both modes should be active. One can transmit or initiate and the other one can receive.

Application

1. Exchanging data
2. Money transfer
3. Social networking

Card emulation mode

Card emulation mode which can be used carry cards virtually instead of physical plastic cards and the people now a days more comfortable with carrying their mobile as well as their work should be done. This mode which can be to read the information and links up the another link. This mode enables application for payment. In card emulation mode there are two types of processing modes one is active mode and the other is active mode. The active mode should be activated when it wants to send and it can be switched to passive when it receives.

3. Objective

The objective of the proposed system is

1). User authentication

This phase plays a important role in mobile payment because the user authentication is not secure means it tends to be low secure and it may lose all the information and its difficult to regain it.

2). Transaction

This plays the next important role after user authentication when we transact the money from one end to another, it should satisfy some conditions and should be secure.

3). Attacks

It may have the possibility for relay attack in NFC enabled devices

Architecture of mobile payment

The user needs to purchase via online ,it should be registered first by giving their details like username password to that particular website, The password which can be like PIN etc., Before started to purchase the user needed to be register in that website when the user started to purchase ,the merchant server needs to authenticate whether he is legitimate or not when it gives username and password. The user name and password should match with already stored password, if it matches it allows the users to purchase. After authentication, the user needs to pay money for the purchase order. The user receives the purchase details from the merchant bank. The user sends the account details from the customer, the bank whether checks whether its legitimate user or not, if it is successful it will transact the money to the merchant bank otherwise it will reject it.

Drawbacks of mobile payment

- 1) Outdated technology and infrastructure
- 2) Cross platform solution
- 3) User adoption is slow
- 4) Difficult to read terms and conditions
- 5) Disputed transaction
- 6) Security concerns

4. proposed method

Proposed architecture

In this proposed method two phases which can be done using protocol and cryptographic mechanism. In terms of security the better algorithm which can be compared and used it in transaction phase. APDU protocol which can be used here for communication and by commands from POS terminal which can initiate the process. The details as follows

Phases of proposed system

In the proposed system, there are three phases are involved.

1. Registration phase
2. Authentication phase
3. Communication or transaction phase

Registration phase

In this phase the user can be used to register to the server. In this registration phase which can be used to collect all the users information ,by using that information when the user wants to login into that system the server checks whether the user is legitimate or not.

Steps

1. The user needs to give username, password and of the mobile device.
 $N1$ =username, password and IMEI number
 $R1$ =Random value

$$N2 = (N1, R1)$$

2. The value of $N2$ which is generated by POS terminal and can be stored in authentication server of POS terminal.

Authentication phase

This phase which is to do check whether the login user is legitimate or not

Steps

1. The user logins the system by their username and password ($N1, R1$)
2. when it done once ,the POS terminal matches the value with the authentication server, when it matches it authenticates the user otherwise it will reject the user and sends the information to the user

$$User = N1, R1$$

$$(Mobile\ device)\ N2 = N2\ (authentication\ server)$$

When it matches, with authentication server it will allow the user to access

Transaction phase

In transaction phase which can be used to communicate with the server for the payment with the bank server. Here APDU protocol is used for the communication between the mobile device and bank server through POS terminal. There are two types of APDU, one is command and other one is response.

Steps

1. Mobile device request POS terminal as byte array sequence to initiate the transaction
2. The POS terminal sends SELECT command to the mobile device and this mobile device will select the application id from which you are going to transfer.
3. After the application ID is selected ,the POS terminal sends GET command
4. The GET command which can be received by the Mobile device, this can fetch the account from the application server which is encrypted by the server sends with IMEI number of the mobile device to the POS terminal
5. The POS terminal sends the purchase details to the bank server with ACCOUNT, the bank server matches the details with it, if it matches it can be allowed to access otherwise it sends the acknowledgement to the mobile device.

Flowchart: Authentication matching process

In this flowchart, it shows the matches to authenticate the user to access the mobile payment

1. In this one ,the user sends username and password as $N1$ and choose random value $R1$ to the POS terminal and the POS terminal which generates $N2$ and matches with the authentication server.
2. If it matches, it allows the user to access otherwise it rejects the request and sends the acknowledgement to the user.

Flowchart: Authentication process

Flowchart: Transaction process

In this transaction phase the users ACCOUNT which fetched from the application server and it can match this data with the database. When it try to match it retrieve the key from the database and decrypt. If it matches, it will approve the transaction otherwise it will reject the transaction and send the acknowledgement to the user.

Security issues

The security mobile payment which should meet the following conditions

1. Confidentiality
2. Integrity
3. Authentication
4. Non-repudiation

Confidentiality

This ensures the confidential information can not be disclosed by the unauthorized user.

Integrity

This one allows only authorized user to modify the data or system

Authentication

It allows the authorized user to access the resources

Non-repudiation

If something goes wrong, it must provide proof.

Public key cryptography mechanism

Cryptographic mechanism which can be done using symmetric and asymmetric. In symmetric there are some disadvantage like two individuals must share a secret key that should be through only secure channel or secure way. public key cryptography has two keys for encryption and decryption.

In this public key cryptography which is not secure when private key is derived from public key in unsecured network.

For public key algorithm is more difficult and it also provides mechanism for signature which can assure the confidence of the message.

There are many cryptographic algorithm are there. Here the two algorithm have been chosen for security

RSA algorithm

RSA, public key cryptography has an advantage and its still unbreakable.

Key generation

1. Let P and Q are the two large prime numbers
2. Let $n=p*q$
3. Let $m=(p-1)(q-1)$
4. choose a small number e which is co-prime to m
5. Find d

For Encryption $C=p^e \% n$

For Decryption $P=C^e \% n$

Comparative analysis of algorithm

1. Input data size
2. Time
3. Throughput

Theoretical analysis

The theoretical analysis is as follows

Power consumption	High
Throughput	Low
confidentiality	Low

Elliptic key cryptography

Elliptical curve cryptography which is more difficult. In this ECC which is good fast at network transmission and computer performance[8][9].

5. Comparison table

In this comparison table the public key cryptographic algorithm for payment can be compared. The RSA algorithm still unbreakable. so for transaction RSA is considered as the best one for payment.

Table for 8 Bit Encryption, Decryption and Time Seconds

Bits	E (ECC)	E (RSA)	D (ECC)	D (RSA)	Total Time in seconds	
					ECC	RSA
80	0.4885	0.0307	1.3267	0.7543	1.8152	0.7850
112	2.2030	0.0299	1.5863	2.7075	3.7893	2.7375
128	3.8763	0.0305	1.7690	6.9409	5.6453	6.9714
114	4.7266	4.7266	2.0022	13.6472	6.7288	13.6962

Table for 64 bit encryption, decryption and time seconds

Bits	E (ECC)	E (RSA)	D (ECC)	D (RSA)	Total Time in seconds	
					ECC	RSA
80	2.1685	0.1366	5.9099	5.5372	8.0784	5.6738
112	9.9855	0.1635	6.9333	20.4108	16.9188	20.5743
128	15.0882	0.1672	7.3584	46.4782	22.4466	46.6454
114	20.2308	0.1385	8.4785	77.7642	28.7093	77.9027

Table for 256 bit encryption, decryption and time seconds

Bits	E (ECC)	E (RSA)	D (ECC)	D (RSA)	Total Time in seconds	
					ECC	RSA
80	7.92	0.55	22.88	19.31	30.80	19.87
112	39.70	0.58	26.33	102.03	66.03	102.61
128	58.43	0.56	24.70	209.60	85.84	210.17
114	77.50	0.57	32.15	311.06	109.65	311.63

6. Experimental tools

Netbeans IDE is a java development tool used to develop java applications.

7. Conclusion

In this one, this mobile payment system is based on NFC enabled devices. In this system the authentication can be done in POS terminal by matching the user data with server data. In this transaction phase APDU protocol can be used with cryptographic mechanism for security purpose. It also have possibilities to reduce the known and the unknown attacks.

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